

How to Design Interactive Walkable Floor Maps - IWF -

What is the idea?

Provide an **interactive learning platform** to...

- Scaffold transitions towards the adoption of **nature-based solutions (NBS)** in cities
- Work with governance, urban planning, education, and children and nature

Who is the audience for this booklet?

This booklet is for...

- Practitioners
- Teachers
- Planners
- Scientists

Own figure

What is needed to design an IWF?

- High-resolution, digital imagery from above (aerial photos, satellite imagery)
- Geographic Information System (GIS)
- Sense of scale and resolution
- Technical infrastructure of a printing company
- Add-ons for overlay material for interaction (QR codes, transparencies, post-its)
- Funding

Own figure

Steps to create the IWF

1. Define the area to cover and get information about the available physical space to roll out the IWF
2. Get the digital imagery from the area of interest in a very high spatial resolution (1 m pixel size or less)
3. Import the imagery into a GIS, set the preferred scale and add further geographical information if needed (e.g. administrative boundaries)
4. Add the legend and metadata (see figure below)
5. Export as PDF with a 300 dpi resolution

Own figure

Steps to make the IWF interactive (example: QR codes)

1. Enter a QR code generator, for instance:
<https://www.qrcode-monkey.com> or
<https://www.the-qrcode-generator.com>
2. (Create first and) copy the link of any project/media/web address (for instance: www.regreen-project.eu)
3. Paste the link into the QR code generator from step 1
4. Modify colour/resolution/size (optional)
5. Double check functionality by scanning the draft QR code using your mobile phone.
6. Download the QR code as image
7. Put this image right at the demonstration site

Steps to make the IWF interactive (example: transparencies)

1. Get an additional dataset of the area you want to present (historical/scenarios/land cover)
2. Set identical scale as for the IWF
3. Export PDF to standard size of transparencies (e.g. DIN A4 / DIN A3)
4. Print this PDF on a transparency
5. Place on top of the area, for demonstration, fix it with a tape if preferred

Own figure

Steps to make the IWF more interactive

- Creatively develop individual, interactive ideas like photo elicitation, post-its or on-the-map-interviews
- The possibilities relate to the targeted audience

Own figures

Material

The material to choose depends on many factors like the budget and permanency. We used PVC with a weight of 510 g/sqm and ~ 400 µm thickness, certified for DIN 4102 B1 and REACH-compliant.

Movability

Pros:

- High flexibility for usage in schools and further education like universities
- Multiple use cases for urban planning in various municipal departments and buildings

Cons:

- Provide storage location
- Laying out the IWF takes manpower and time

Own figure

How much does the IWF cost and who are the experts?

Manpower costs

~ 500 € / map

You can find map making expertise at research institutions, urban/environmental planning bureaus, universities, NGOs

Printing costs

~ 30 € - 40 € / sqm

Get advice from advertisement companies with expertise in printing ad banners

Shipping costs (1000 km)

~ 200 € / map,
not necessary when locally
printed

If not printed locally, try to send a parcel (e.g. with [DHL](#)) otherwise hire a cargo company

Further information

- Elze, Sebastian, Banzhaf, Ellen, Jensen, Anne, & Læssøe, Jeppe. (2023). Interactive Walkable Floor Maps (IWFs). GI_Salzburg23, Salzburg, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8341267>
- <https://www.regreen-project.eu>

Imprint

© REGREEN EU Project publishing

1st Edition, 09/2023

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Created using bookcreator.com

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

EC grant agreement No 821016